

DIFFERENT ASPECTS OF “CAN”, “COULD” AND “TO BE ABLE TO”

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Abstract: *The distinctions and similarities between modal verbs like "can" and "could" and auxiliary verbs like "to be able to" are discussed in this article. The rules for using the abovementioned modal and auxiliary verbs in each of the three tenses (past, present, and future) are explained separately. In addition to this, you have also clarified and provided other instances of when these modal verbs and auxiliary verbs may be used interchangeably and when they can't. As a result, I recommend that you read this article, and I hope that you really like it and gain profit from it.*

Key Words: *modal verb, main verb, auxiliary verb, can, could, may, might, to be able to, can have, could have, to be unable to.*

There is no doubt that these terms ("can," "could," and "to be able to") refer to a person's ability, awareness, and potential. Additionally, they're also used to express someone's permission to accomplish something. The auxiliary verbs "can" and "could" are modal verbs. Despite the fact that "to be able to" is not an auxiliary verb; it is a main verb that employs the verb "to be". For convenience, we use the phrase "able to."

One of our most basic rules is that both "can" and "could" are followed by an infinitive without "to". For example, Feruz can drive a car. Uncle Tohir could speak seven languages.

What is more, "Cannot" or "can't" is the negative version of "can." The main rule is in there! The word 'cannot' is never written as "can not". Example: I'm sorry, but I can't hear you. (I'm sorry, but I can't hear you.) Aziz can't swim in rivers. Furthermore, "Could not" or "couldn't" is the negative version of "could." For instance, Anvar couldn't see anything since it was so black. They couldn't get a good night's sleep. You may either place "not" or another negative word in front of "able to" to construct the negative of "to be able to." I haven't been able to study for the exam. We are unable to afford the entrance fee.

Moreover, the words "can," "could," and "be able to" are all used to describe someone's ability to do something. To discuss about present

ability, you might say "can" or "be able to." "To be able to" is a more formal expression than "can." I can show some examples like these:

- You can all read and write.
- All of the animals are able to move around and lie down.
- Nodira only nodded, unable to speak.

In addition to this, in the present, the word "could" is also used to describe ability, but it has a different connotation. When you state that someone could do something, you're implying that they have the ability to do it but don't. For example, we could do a lot more to educate people in this country.

The next one is that, when talking about former abilities, you use "could" or a past version of "be able to." For instance, he could run faster than everyone else. For the most part, they couldn't read or write. I was unable to respond to their inquiries.

When you say that someone was able to do something, you typically imply that they were capable of doing it and that they did it. "Could" does not have this meaning. You may see some examples like these.

- He was able to return to work after two weeks in bed.
- The farmers were able to pay the wages of their workers.

On the one hand, you say someone could have done something if you want to claim they had the ability to do something but didn't. For example:

- You could have delivered it to me in its entirety.
- You could have been a tad more cautious.

On the other hand, you say they could not have done something if you want to suggest that someone did not do something because they lacked the ability to do it. For instance, I couldn't have met with you because I was in London at the time.

You say he or she used to be able to do something if you want to suggest that someone had the capacity to perform something in the past but no longer has it.

- I used to be able to sleep anywhere I wanted.
- You used to be able to see the house from here before.

To talk about your capacity in the future, you use a future version of "to be able to."

- That is a question I will be able to answer tomorrow.

Furthermore, in reporting structures, the word "could" is frequently employed. If a student says, "I can speak Uzbek," you would normally describe it as, "She stated she could speak Uzbek."

Furthermore, "be able to" is frequently used after modals such as "might" or "should," as well as verbs such as "desire," "hope," and "expect. I may be able to assist you.

- You might be able to acquire some additional cash. From here, you should be able to see it. She'd be unable to go out on her own.

- Do you think you'll be able to pull it off?

However, after any other verb, don't use "can" or "could."

Moreover, the "-ing" version of "to be able to" is used. For instance, he appreciated being able to debate politics with Veronica. "Can" and "could" do not have a "-ing" form.

The words "can" and "could" are used in conjunction with verbs like "see," "hear," and "smell" to indicate that someone is or was aware of something through one of their senses.

- I can detect odors.

- Aziza could only see a few stars in the sky.

What is more, the words "could" and "can" are used to describe present and future possibilities. When you mention "could," you're implying that something has a chance of being true.

- It's not something you should consume. It could be toxic.

- He was sentenced to prison in February and could be freed next year.

The words "might" and "may" are interchangeable. For example: It might be a trap. Kathy's job may even be jeopardized.

Stay on top! When expressing the potential that something isn't true, don't use "could not." You should instead use the words "might not" or "may not." It's possible that it might not be doable. (*not* It's possible that it could not be doable.) or It may not be simple. (*not* It cannot be simple.)

You use the words "cannot" or "could not" to express that something is impossible to be true.

- You cannot possibly know what damage you have caused.

- Stealing couldn't possibly be true.

When you mention "can," you're implying that something is conceivable at times. For instance, it can be the best example. Sudden shifts can have a detrimental impact on certain people.

When you say "could," you're expressing that something was true in the past. He could have been alone in the house.

The words "may have" and "might have" are equivalent.

- She might well have looked up the facts on the internet.

- It may have been a slain bird.

You may also use "could have" to express the potential of something being true in the past, even if it was not.

- It could've been a lot worse.
- As a lawyer, Akram could have made a fortune.

Take better care of! Use "could not have" instead of "could have" to express the possibility that something was not true. You should say "might not have" or "may not have" instead. She might have been unaware of the password.

The term "could not have" is used to express the impossibility of something being true. Example:

- It couldn't have been an easy choice.
- We couldn't have been spotted by the man at all.

The words "can" and "could" are used to express whether or not someone is permitted to accomplish something.

- You can withdraw cash from any cash machine.
- He could come over and use my computer.

To express that someone is or was banned for doing something, the words "cannot" and "could not" are used. Her parents told her that she couldn't go out during the week.

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